

IDENTIFICATION OF REGULATIONS AND RULES IN INTERNATIONAL MULTIMODAL TRANSPORTATION

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***Abstract:** Multimodal transportation is the transportation of goods under an agreement with one carrier using different modes of transport. Transportation takes place in stages, and combinations of river, road, sea, air and rail transport may vary. The main condition is at least two delivery methods in one route. The carrier has the right to use the transport of other counterparties, but all responsibility to the customer lies with the general contractor from whom the transportation is ordered. The organization of multimodal cargo transportation must begin with integrated route planning.*

Relevance. Multimodal refers to the transportation of goods using various modes of transport. Accordingly, by multimodal transport we will understand the complex of modes of transport involved in the transportation of goods along the entire route. In some foreign sources, the term multimodal corresponds to the term intermodal.

Purpose and objectives of the study. Modern trends in the globalization of the world economy involve the construction of complex supply chains, in which there is interaction between parties, usually located on different continents. The development of such relationships cannot be imagined without the effective organization of a network of multimodal transportation. In recent years, due to the strengthening of trade and economic ties between countries, there is an obvious tendency to increase the volume of goods transported in multimodal traffic. At the same time, the organization and implementation of this type of transportation are influenced by numerous factors of the external and internal environment. The risks associated with the organization of

the transport process and its interaction with market entities are increasing. Problematic issues are uninterrupted, reliable transportation, compliance with delivery times without loss and at minimal cost. The solution of these issues necessitates the development of a high-quality material flow management process in multimodal transportation, on which the achievement of competitive advantages by an enterprise depends.

Materials and methods. However, to date there is no internationally agreed terminology for transportation that is carried out with the participation of several modes of transport. Therefore, the development of a unified terminology, in combination with the improvement of the modern international system of sectoral legal regulation of multimodal transportation, seems to be an important and urgent task. At the same time, in addition to developing a single conceptual apparatus for multimodal transportation, it is necessary to develop a standardized and harmonized semantic structure of terms that will be convenient for transport service providers, logistics operators, shippers and other participants in international supply chains.

Results and discussions. International multimodal transportation is usually defined as transportation using several modes of transport, carried out under the

responsibility of one carrier under a single transport document and at a single through rate. To date, in the economic and legal literature, such transportation is often called "combined", "mixed", "intermodal". This terminological confusion creates a number of difficulties for the parties to the transportation and the law enforcer. In addition, there is no single approach to the definition of multimodal transportation itself, which largely explains the absence of an imperative fixation of this institution in the legislation of many states and a generally accepted proclamation at the international level.

Conclusions. The main features of multimodal transportation are the phased use of several types of transport, the responsibility of one carrier for transportation, reloading and safety of products. This type of transportation is carried out according to the "door to door" scheme - from the sender to the recipient. Often there is confusion in terms when the concepts of multimodal, intermodal, unimodal transportation are mixed. The determining factor is the degree of responsibility of the carrier: Unimodal transportation is not accompanied by reloading of goods in transit; intermediate storage in warehouses is excluded from the scheme. The main mode of transport is road transport, the responsibility for the cargo lies with one carrier.

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